

On Damage Mechanisms In Randomly Oriented Short fiber composites.

Part I. Tensile with elastic release on virgin and impacted specimens

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ABSTRACT.

The general objective of this study is to identify the basic damage mechanisms in randomly oriented short fiber composites by using a local experimental approach, based on the combination of amplitude analysis and microscopic observations.

Damage mechanisms identified in tensile loading on virgin specimens are compared with those identified in tensile test on impacted specimens, in order to determine the residual damage modes.

The contribution of each damage mechanism is quantified, to be used in local damage model.

1. INTRODUCTION.

Randomly oriented short fiber composites are emerging due to increasing concern about the most compromise of technological solutions choosing these materials. Weight savings, suitability of low cost and high volume production of geometrically complex parts, present these composites as one of the most promising candidates for automotive structural and other applications.

The initiation and growth of damage occur according to complex failure mechanisms, which are widely dependent on material structure and also on the loading conditions .

The identification of damage mechanisms of these composites have constituted the object of several researches, using acoustic emission monitoring [1,2], using an experimental investigation (X-ray, ...etc.) to determine the damage growth and the residual toughness [3,4], and using amplitude distribution of acoustic events as well as microscopic observations [5].

In this study, we propose an experimental approach based on damage detection techniques by acoustic emission and microscopic observations (S.E.M), which have contributed towards the identification of all basic damage mechanisms under tensile loading with successive elastic release on virgin specimens. These previous mechanisms are compared with those identified on specimen impacted at different levels of failure energy, then subjected to tensile loading with elastic release.

KEY WORDS : Damage Mechanisms, Short Fibers, Impact, Acoustic Emission, Identification.

2. MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE.

The material of this study is a glass fiber epoxy sheet moulding compound, where the fibers are randomly oriented and assembled in bundles with constant length (25. mm). According to the fiber diameter and bundles, three types of material are defined and designed as material A, B and C. Specifics material aspects ratio are given in table 1.

Material designation	(L/d) _{Fiber}	(L/d) _{Bundel}
A	2500	71.4
B	1785	31.25
C	1389	19.25

Table1. Specifics Material Data.

The fiber concentration is characterised by two value, the first is a locale fiber concentration $(V_f)_m$, which represents the volume fraction of fibers in bundles and the second $(V_m)_c$ the volume fraction of bundles in the composites [6]. However, when elaborating material, one condition must be verified :

$$(V_f) = 0.5 \quad (1)$$

and $(V_f) = (V_f)_m \cdot (V_m)_c$

Three types of tests were conducted in this study.

2.1 Tensile test with elastic release on virgin specimens.

This test was conducted according to AFNOR tensile test (AFNOR EN61), using loading speed of 2 mm/min. Specimens were instrumented with stain gages and their geometry is shown in figure 1.

Figure .1 tensile test specimen geometry

2.2 Impact test

The conventional Charpy impact test was conducted according to AFNOR impact test (AFNOR T57-108), using impact velocity of 2.93 m/s and an impactor of 2400 g.

The total impact energy is evaluated on ten plate specimens for each kind of material , the plate specimens are 60 mm long and 14 mm large with 14. mm deep.

Figure 3.a Schematic and observation of mechanisms corresponding to area 1.

Area 2 (A2.) corresponds to the amplitudes between 45 and 64 dB, and is associated to the matrix / matrix friction and the delamination between packets of bundles (pseudo delamination), which are due to the coalescence of matrix microcracking. In terms of acoustic events, the peaks representing the delamination are lower than the peak corresponding to matrix microcracking.(figure 3.b).

Figure 3.b Schematic and observation of mechanisms corresponding to area 2.

Area 3 (A3.) corresponds to the peak around 64 dB and is associated to interface decohesion. This mechanism is very important because it is able to favour the pseudo-delamination (Area 1.) or debonding fiber / matrix friction and according to interface decohesion appearance, at border bundles or bundles at the depth of packet (Figure 3.c).

Figure 3.c Schematic and observation of mechanisms corresponding to area 3.

Area 4 (A4.) corresponds to the amplitudes between 64 and 90 dB, this area is very dependent on interface decohesion, when it occurs at bundles of depth in packet. The damage mechanisms identified at these amplitudes are fiber / matrix friction and fiber debonding. (Figure 3.d).

2.3 Tensile test with elastic release on impacted specimens.

In order to obtain the evolution of "Residual" damage mechanisms, a tensile test with successive elastic release was conducted on specimens impacted at 80%, 70%, 50% and 30% of the total impact energy. The geometry of specimens is shown in figure 1. The different levels of impact energy were obtained by varying the angle of impactor support, because it was not possible to change the mass of impactor.

3. IDENTIFICATION OF DAMAGE MECHANISMS.

3.1 In tensile test.

In specimens subjected to tensile loading, the basic failure modes are identified by combination of two experimental techniques of damage investigation.

Using a piezoelectric sensor connected to an acquisition system, the acoustic emission has been recorded during tensile loading and analysed in terms of amplitude. Microscopic observations of damaged specimen allow to confirm the advent of each failure mechanism.

The details of methodology of the damage mechanisms discrimination are given in references [2],[7] and [8].

The different amplitude distributions have permitted to distinguish five areas on curves. Each one of these area is characterised by an interval of amplitudes values and associated to one or several basic damage modes. Typical amplitude distribution in tensile loading is illustrated in figure 3. The areas are defined as following.

Figure 2. Typical Amplitude Distribution.and Areas definition

Area 1 (A1.) corresponds to low amplitudes (40-45 dB) and is associated to matrix microcracking (Figure 3.a), which is the dominant failure mechanism and can govern the advent of the remaining mechanisms in tensile loading.

Figure 3.d Schematic and observation of mechanisms corresponding to area 4.

Area 5 (A5.) corresponds to the amplitudes between 95 and 100 dB, the mechanisms advent in this amplitude interval represent generally bundles shattering because of the total fiber /matrix interface decohesion and fiber breakage due to the stress concentration at their ends. (Figure 3.e).

Figure 3.e Schematic and observation of mechanisms corresponding to area 5.

Fiber breakage is not considered as a damage mechanism, because when using a local approach for modelization of damaged material, the elementary volume is considered as completely damaged in this case.

In order to compare the three types of materials in terms of damage mechanisms advent and acoustic events activity, samples amplitude distributions versus acoustic events are shown in figure 4.

It has been noted that in terms of matrix microcracking (A1) and pseudo-delamination between packets (A2), the material (A) presents the lower acoustic activity than the materials (B) and (C). Thus, the material (A) is most efficient to check the damage growth by microcracking or pseudo-delamination.

Figure 4. Representative amplitude distribution for materials A,B And C.

The material (C) presents a low number of acoustic events corresponding to area 4 (A4.), due to the low fiber debonding when happening.

It has been noted also, that in this case the matrix / matrix friction and the pseudo-delamination correspond to an intense acoustic activity because the interface decohesion have occurred at border bundles and not in those of depth. So, this can justify the almost absence of the area 5, which is not the case of material (B).

Moreover, the peak around the value of 64 dB, can give some informations about the quality of the interface according to acoustic activity.

3.2 Tensile on impacted specimens.

The same experimental methodology of damage investigation was adopted in tensile test on impacted specimens, in the aim to identify the basic failure modes in this case.

The different amplitude distribution present an identical repartition of damage mechanism as those identified in tensile loading .

It has been noted the absence of certains peaks, when the specimens were previously impacted. Indeed, it has been remarked the absence of the peaks corresponding to matrix microcracking (40-45 dB) and the attenuation of those representing the pseudo-delamination (45-64 dB), these remarks are particularly valid for the upper proportion levels of impact energy.

Furthermore, the remaining mechanisms (interface decohesion, separation between bundles, fiber debonding ... etc.) present a low lessening in their acoustic activity (Figure 5).

These absence and attenuation of acoustic activity are explained as following :

When impacting (particularly at upper levels of energy), the first damage mechanism which appears is the matrix microcracking, after that, the delamination between packets partially occurs, according to the energy level.

It is, therefore, obvious that the matrix was completely damaged and the packets of bundles were partially separated. So , when these impacted specimen are subjected to tensile loading the remaining damage mechanisms appear, constituting the "residual" damage mechanisms.

This experimental methodology allows to discriminate the damage mechanisms happening during impact test.

Figure 5. Representative amplitude aistribution for impacted specimens

The total impact energy values were calculated by integrating the area under the impact force versus time curves, and accounting for the impact velocity. (Table 2)

Material	A	B	C
Total impact energy (J)	5.81	5.40	6.84
Standard deviation	0.33	0.41	0.57

Table. 2. Total Impact Energy.

Figure 7. Sample impact force versus time curves

We note that the materials (A) and (B) have almost the same values of total impact energy and peak force, because these two materials have similar structural parameters corresponding to matrix and bundles, this remark is confirmed by the previous comments.

Material (C), which have the upper value of impact energy (6.84 J), in spite of the low value of peak energy (6.84 J), this is justified by the absence of coarse fall of the impact force after the peak which is represented by an increasing of this zone.

4. EVALUATION OF A MECHANISM'S CONTRIBUTION IN TOTAL FAILURE.

The experimental approach previously proposed, gives a qualitative information about the damage mechanisms. However, in the aim to modelize these different damage modes, it is necessary to propose a quantitative approach to evaluate the contribution of each mechanism considered separately, in the global failure of the material.

Using the representative amplitude distribution of acoustic events, for a specimen under a known loading conditions, it is possible to evaluate the degree of contribution of each mechanism by calculating numerically the area corresponding to the considered mechanism.

The ratio of this calculated area to the total area under the events versus amplitudes curve, give the mechanism's contribution in the global failure. and is designated by (P_i)

$$P_i = \frac{A_i}{\sum_{i=1}^5 A_i} \quad i=1,5 \quad (2)$$

(i) is the number of mechanism.

These different rates allow to weighting the global elasticity tensor of damaged material, like:

$$\tilde{\Lambda} = \frac{\sum_{i=1} P_i \tilde{\Lambda}_i}{\sum_{i=1} P_i} = \frac{1}{100} \sum_{i=1} P_i \tilde{\Lambda}_i \quad (3)$$

(i=1,5)

$\tilde{\Lambda}_i$ Elasticity tensor of damaged material by the mechanism (i)

$\tilde{\Lambda}$ Global elasticity tensor of damaged material.

5. CONCLUSION

Damage mechanisms in short fiber composites are identified under tensile loading and impact, some concluding remarks can be done.

- Impact energy alone cannot be an indicator for initiation and growth of damage mechanisms.
- Amplitude distribution curves have highlighted a certain order in the advent of damage mechanisms.
- Matrix microcracking and the pseudo-delamination are the only failure mechanisms occurring during impact test.
- Interface decohesion can govern the evolution of the pseudo-delamination or the fibers debonding during tensile loading.
- The proposed local experimental approach can quantify the contribution of each basic damage mode for a given loading.

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